

Report of: Tour to Southern Marâṭha Country in search of Sanskrit manuscripts.

By

Dr. Bühler ¹⁾.

To Sir A. Grant, Bart.,

Director of Public Instruction, Bombay.

Sir, — I have the honour to place before you my report on the results of my Tour in the Southern Marâṭha Country and Kanara, made in November and December 1866 and January 1867, in search of Sanskrit Manuscripts for the Government of Bombay.

2. According to your instructions I started from Puna on November the 2nd. As the Quarter Master General declared himself unable to provide me with a tent for my journey, I had throughout on my tour to restrict myself to those parts of the country where I could find Traveller's Bungalows, or other suitable house accommodation. I followed, therefore, with occasional excursions to places within easy reach from a Traveller's Bungalow, the main road which leads through Sattara to Belgaum and Dharwar, and thence through Hubali to Karwar, and returned by the same route. The chief towns visited by me were Wâi, Sattara, Pâl, Karhâd, Ashte, Kolhapur, Sângli, Miraj, Kaghul, Nipâni, Sankeshwar, Belgaum, Dharwar, Nargund, Hubali, Yellapur, and Karwar.

3. In attempting to carry out your orders, I felt that, considering the greatness of the field of Sanskrit literature, it would be necessary, in order to fulfil the generous intentions of the Bombay Government, and to further really the interest of Sanskrit philology, to settle in advance certain principles which were to guide me in my operations. A primary object, of course, must be to search for Sanskrit works, hitherto unobtainable, the recovery of which might contribute to the solution of some of the many pending questions of Sanskrit philology.

But besides keeping this object in view, the peculiar circumstances of Bombay seemed to make it advisable for me to direct

1) Eingesandt an Prof. Weber in Berlin, dem die beigefügten Noten zugehören.

my attention also to certain other classes of manuscripts. Unlike the other Presidencies of India, Bombay possesses no large collection of Sanskrit manuscripts. In Bombay itself there is only a comparatively speaking, small (though valuable) number of manuscripts belonging to the Bombay Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society. There are a dozen volumes in the Elphinstone College Library, and perhaps as many more in the High Court. Nor will the Bombay Sanskritist find much in the libraries of the public institutions at Puṇa. There are perhaps a hundred works in the old Puṇa College Library, kept in the Vishrâmbâg, and sixty-seven more in the collection procured by Dr. Haug for the Government of Bombay, and deposited in the Puṇa College.

Under these circumstances it was the obvious duty of any person collecting new manuscripts to try to supplement the existing Libraries of Bombay and Puṇa, and to direct his attention to the acquisition of important works, which though perhaps easily obtainable elsewhere, were wanting in the collections here, and also, in some cases, of new and better manuscripts of already accessible books.

A third consideration which must influence the collector was the necessity of providing suitable materials for those young Sanskritists who have undertaken to assist in the edition of the Bombay Series of Sanskrit Classics, which was proposed last year by Dr. Kielhorn and myself, and received so cordial an approbation from you and from the Government of Bombay.

4. In order to realize these objects, firstly was prepared a list of such works, the acquisition of which seemed particularly desirable, and copies of this list were placed in the hands of all Shastris and other persons, who showed themselves ready to assist in the search for manuscripts.

Secondly all obtainable lists of books which were in the possession of Shastris and other native gentlemen in the places visited, were collected and carefully examined. Whenever anything promising to be of interest was found in them, the manuscripts were examined either by myself or by my Shastri and other assistants.

Thirdly I invited the Shastris and Sanskrit Scholars of every town visited to meet me, and used these meetings to explain the objects of my mission, to make inquiries regarding manuscripts, and to discuss with them in their own sacred language, interesting points of Sanskrit philology and letters. I hoped, by a personal acquaintance, and by showing a real interest in their ancient language and culture, to remove, or at least to lessen the aversion, which natives generally have, to giving or even showing their books to strangers, and particularly to foreigners.

5. The first result of these arrangements was that I received a number of lists of manuscripts from private libraries existing in Puṇa, Sattara, Kelgaum, Ashte, Kolhapur, Sângli, Nipâni, Sankesh-

war, Yamkhandmardi, Belgaum, Dharwar, Nargund, Navalgund, and Hubali, amongst which those of Mr. Bhau Shastri Dikshit at Sattara, and of Mr. Limaye at Ashte, are by far the most important. The libraries of these two gentlemen surpass all the rest in extent, and are also richest in unique or rare books. Mr. Limaye's collection contains 147 pothis or bundles, and that of Mr. Dikshit appears to be even larger. The former seems to have been only recently made, whilst the latter is, partially at least, very old. A great many of the manuscripts which Mr. Dikshit placed at my disposal with a liberality far in advance to the general spirit of the Brahman possessors of libraries, were very ancient, and written in Kayasth and Guzerat handwriting. Next after these two the list of the Râjâs of Kolhapur and Sângli, that of a Shastri at Kolhapur, and one from Nargund deserve to be mentioned.

Unfortunately none of the lists, with the exception of that from Ashte, gives more than short titles of the works, which are frequently quite insufficient to identify them with certainty, and in several cases personal examination of the libraries convinced me that the lists were untrustworthy. Important works are entered under wrong titles, and often books which still figure in the lists, on inquiry turn out to be lost. Though therefore most of these lists are of, comparatively speaking, small value, still it might be of interest to Sanskritists, if selections of the contents of the more correct ones were made public. For I do not doubt, that in many cases it would be possible to procure copies or collations of the works contained in them for Sanskritists, who might be anxious to have such.

6. The number of manuscripts bought, copied, or ordered for copying, amounts up to the present time to nearly two hundred, and it is to be hoped that eventually their number will be increased as fresh lists and offers of single books and even larger collections continue to be made.

I shall now proceed to enumerate the more important acquisitions. It is, however, for the present impossible for me to enter into detailed descriptions of these works, as in very many cases I have only been able to obtain a cursory inspection of them:

I. Manuscripts of the Vedas and Vedangas, and of their commentaries.

A. *Brâhmanas.*

1. The Gopatha Brâhmana of the Atharva Veda.

MSS. of this work are extremely rare. A complete copy exists at Ashte, from which this copy has been ordered. Regarding the work and the MS. in London, see M. Müller, *Hist. Sansk. Lit.* p. 446—455.

2. Ekavâi or Ekavâyî Brâhmana. Ashte Pothi No. 121.

I am as yet unable to give any information regarding this

book, as I never found it mentioned anywhere¹⁾, and I was not allowed to examine the MS. myself. As it is placed in the Ashte Catalogue amongst the MSS. belonging to the Atharva Veda, it may be supposed that it belongs to this Veda. According to my Shastri's extracts, the manuscript begins:

Sa vai sambhârân sambharati tadvâ enâcitthâcctthâccâ (?)
Sambhâra iti tadeva²⁾ sambhârânâm sambhâratvam (ekavâi
Brâhmaṇam).

And it ends:

Tasmâd âhuç câturmâsyâyâjinam (?) nanuvindatiti paramâm³⁾
hy eva sa lokam paramâm jitim jayatiti [iti ekavâyî brahma-
nasyâshtamodhyâyah].

It may be observed that the Ashte list, which is rich in works belonging to the Atharvaveda mentions also an Atharvaveda bhâshya. But though I carefully examined the bundle in which it ought to have been lying it was not to be found. In its stead lay an accentuated MS. of the Samhitâ of the A. V. Mr. Limaye states that the bundle never contained anything else than this book, and that the statement in the list is a mistake.

B. Sûtras.

1. The Hiraṇyakeçi Sûtras, Çrauta Gṛihya and Dharma complete.

One MS. of the text, and one MS. in which the first and last are accompanied by the Commentaries of Mahâdeva, the second by that of Mâtridatta.

2. The Âpastamba Dharmasûtra, with the Commentary of Haradatta.

This work, which is one of the oldest authorities of the Hindu law, appears to be rare in the public libraries of Europe. In India a good number of copies are to be had.

Both the text and the commentary are of great interest also for this reason, that they are nearly literally the same as the Hiraṇyakeçidharma and its Commentary by Mahâdeva. Both Commentaries, also, are entitled „Ujvalâ“.

3. The Âpastamba Çulvasûtra.
4. The Baudhâyana sûtras, both Çrauta and Gṛihya, with the Commentary of Bhavasvâmin.
5. The Kauçikagṛihyasûtra.

This is the same work as that which Dr. Haug brought from Guzerat under the title Âtharvanagṛihyasûtra, and as that which is

1) Es ist das erste Buch des Çatapatha Brâhmaṇa in der Kâṇva-Schule (ekapâdikâ), vgl. meine Ausgabe des Ç. B. preface pag. X. Verz. der B. S. H. p. 43.

2) Es ist zu lesen: yad vâ enâñ itthâ cetthâ ca sambharati tad eva.

3) Lies: °mâsyâyâjinam nâ'nuvindantiti paramam.

described in the Berlin Catalogue, No. 362, under the title *Kauçikasûtra*.

6. The Bharadvâjasûtra, with the Kapardibhâshya.

C. Prâtiçâkhyas and Pariçishtas.

1. The Prâtiçâkhyas of the Black Yajurveda, with the commentary called Tribhâshyaratna. MSS. of this work are not very rare on this side of India, though few if any have found their way into the public libraries, or to Europe.
2. The Prâtiçâkhyas of the White Yajurveda, with the Commentary of Uvata, that called the Jyotsnâ¹⁾, and portions of a Commentary by Anantabhaṭṭa, the son of Nâgadeva.
3. Pariçishtas of the White Yajurveda; chiefly on the pronunciation of the texts, amongst which the Bṛihadyâjnavalkya Çikshâ, the Kâtyâyaniya Çikshâ, the Bhâshikasûtra of Kâtyâyana, the Pratijñâsûtra of Kâtyâyana, and the Avasânasûtra of Vyâdi, may be specified.

The Bhâshikasûtra, attributed to Kâtyâyana, an analysis of which has been prepared by Dr. Kielhorn, settles the question regarding the accents of the Çatapatha-brâhmaṇa, and shows that this Brâhmaṇa is to be recited with two accents only²⁾. All these small treatises were, I believe, hitherto unknown to the Sanskrit scholars of Europe.

4. The Atharvaveda Pariçishtas.

Two complete copies of the seventy-four Pariçishtas of this Veda, as well as one copy containing the first half, have come to light. One of the complete copies belonging to Mr. Dikshit at Sattara, seems to be much more correct than the defective Berlin copy, and the apograph of a Guzerat manuscript deposited by Dr. Haug in the Puṇa College. With the help of these new manuscripts it would, no doubt, be possible to bring out an edition of the Niḡhaṇṭu, and of the other interesting pieces which the collection contains.

5. Âçvalâyana Pariçishtas.

These form a supplement to the Gṛihyasûtras of Âçvalâyana.

II. Poetry and Fiction.

The following MSS. were procured with a view that they should furnish Materials for the Bombay series of Sanskrit Classics:

1. Kirâtârjuniya, with the Commentary of Mallinâtha (two copies).
2. Çiçupâlavadhâ, with the Commentary of Mallinâtha.
3. Naishadhîya, with a Commentary.
4. Nalodaya, with Commentary (two copies).

1) Durch die freundliche Güte Prof. Bühler's habe ich kürzlich eine Abschrift dieses Jyotsnâ genannten Commentars erhalten, vgl. Ind. Stud. X, 433.

2) S. Ind. Stud. X, 397—441.

5. *Mricchakaṭika*, with a Commentary (2 copies).
6. *Vikramorvaṣī*, with a Commentary.
7. *Mālatīmādhava*, with a Commentary.
8. *Ratnāvalī*, with a Commentary.
9. *Mudrārākshasa*, with a Commentary.
10. *Veṅṣaṃhāra*, with a Commentary.
11. *a.* *Kādambarī*, Text and Commentary by Vaidyanātha Pāyagunde to the first half.
b. Text with Commentary on the entire work by two Jainas, teacher and pupil.

The latter lived under the protection of Jellaleddin Akbar Shah. The MS. is very old, and comes from Guzerat. It, most probably, is not much later than the times of the writer of the commentary.

12. *a.* *Daçakumāracarita*, with a Commentary by Kavindra Sarasvatī. (2 copies, one imperfect).
b. The text with the metrical introduction of *Apyayāmātya*, in 3 paricchedas.
13. *Bhartrihari's çatakas*, with an anonymous Commentary (2 copies).

Besides, copies were obtained of the *Nāgānanda nāṭaka*, *Sūhāsanadvātriṅçatī*, *Çukasaptatī*, *Vetālapañcaviṅçatī*, the *Nalāyana*; and of some smaller poems.

III. Philosophy.

On the *Sāṅkhya* system, the Commentary of Aniruddha on the *Sūtras* of Kapila was procured, and the *Rājamārtāṇḍa*, or Commentary by Bhoja, prince of Dhār, on the *Yogasūtras* of Patanjali.

In *Nyāya* the oldest Commentary on the *Sūtras* of Gautama, the famous *Vātsyāyana bhāshya* was discovered at Ashte, and a set of the current authorities, such as the *Jagadīçī*, *Mathurānāthī*, portions of the *Gadādhari*, the *Kiraṇāvalī*, *Tarkāmṛita*, were partly bought old, partly ordered to be copied. Many of the latter books were found at Dharwar, where, as well as in all cities inhabited by the followers of *Madhvācārya*, the *Nyāya* is particularly cultivated. It is there, in fact, the only branch of Sanskrit letters, with the exception of *Vedānta*, which is generally studied. For the *Pūrvamīmāṃsā* the *Tantravārttika* of Kumārila with a Commentary, was promised by a Shastri at Kolhapur, in whose possession it is. In *Vedānta* several works belonging to the *Dvaita-School* of *Madhvācārya* were procured through the help of two native gentlemen, belonging to the Department of Public Instruction at Belgaum. The *Mādhva* Brahmans showed themselves the most bigoted and illiberal of all. Though a number of them were willing to talk with me on the secular branches of Sanskrit letters, such as *Nyāya*, Law, &c., they refused altogether to discuss their *Vedānta*, and to part with or to show me any of their books. Had it not been for two of

them, who had received an English education and are now in the Department, I should most likely have got nothing. Amongst the Mâdhva books copied or being copied I mention the Vedânta sūtra-bhâshya, the Anubhâshya, the Chandrikâ, the Sudhâ, the Madhva-vijaya or life of Madhva, the Vâyustotra, and the Bhârata and Bhâgavatatâtparyas. Besides the books of the Madhva sects, I ordered also a number of works belonging to the Lingâyats, who likewise profess to base their doctrines on the Vedânta Sûtras. Several lists of the works which they esteem highest, together with notes on the authors and a quantity of interesting details regarding the worship and ceremonies of this sect, were given to me by two educated members of the caste. And even a copy of their fundamental work, the Nîlakanthabhâshya on the Vedântasûtras was promised.

IV. Grammar.

A. System of Pânini.

1. The Mahâbhâshya of Patañjali.

In the course of my researches a great many copies of this famous work, accompanied by the glosses of Kaiyaṭa and Nâgojî, have come to light. Though it did not seem advisable to have a copy made of the book, because a new copy would most likely be very expensive, and old MSS. will be procurable in time at a much cheaper rate, still it will be interesting to Sanskritists to know that any one who wishes to prepare an edition of the work can find in this Presidency ample materials for it. Several of the copies shown to me are old and good, and it might be possible to obtain a loan of them for collation.

2. *Kâçikâvivaraṇapañcikâ*, by Jinendrabuddhi.

A part of this work, the oldest commentary on the Kâçikâ vṛitti of Pânini's Sûtras, was found in Sattara in the library of Mr. Dikshit. The owner was not aware of its existence, and in the Catalogue it was entered as Kâçikavivaraṇa. The MS. contains the comment on the second Adhyâya of Pânini, and is numbered f. 170—238. It is written in the so-called Kâyasth hand-writing, and apparently very old. The Vivaraṇapañcika, hitherto, was thought to be lost. The recovery even of this portion has a peculiar interest, as its author was a *Bauddha*. He is called Bodhisattvadeçîya, „almost a Bodhisattva“, in the subscriptions at the end of each Pâda. The book must therefore have a considerable antiquity.

3. The Padamañjarî of Haradatta.

The well known commentary on the Kâçikâvṛitti; younger than the preceding. (Adhyâyas II. III. IV. (twice); V. VI. VII. VIII.)

4. The Prayogavivekasamgraha of Vararuci, with a Commentary.

This work is written in Çlokas, and contains three Paṭalas (25. Çl. in all). It gives syntactical rules according to Pânini's

system. I have not seen it noticed by any European Sanskritist. A good many verses from it are quoted in modern Indian books on elementary grammar. A fragment of the same work, copied in Madras, is in my own possession.

5. *Mâdhaviya Dhâtuṣṛitti.*

Two copies were found of this work, which, though well known in Europe, is rare and little used in India, at least in this Presidency. Both the Manuscripts have a peculiar interest thereby that they are very old. One of them in a library at Nargund is dated Çake dvivedabhûmite 'tha vikrame, in the Çaka year, measured by the two, the four, and the one, and (corresponding to) the Saṃvatsara called Vikrama. It follows from the latter statement that the Çaka year meant is 1442 or 1520 A. C. The MS. was, therefore, written about a hundred years after Sâyaṇa.

6. The *Prakriyâkaumudî*, with the Commentary of Viṭhalâcârya.

7. The *Laghuçabdenduçekhara* of Nâgojibhaṭṭa.

Besides these larger works some smaller ones, such as a *Phit-sûtravṛitti*, two *Uṇâdivṛittis*, one by Gaṅgâdhara, and one a fragment, the *Taddhita kosha* of Bhavadeva, Sîradeva's *paribhâshâs*, were procured.

B. The *Kâtantravyâkaraṇa*, with the Commentary of Durgasiṅha.

C. *Sârasvatavyâkaraṇa*.

D. The *Haimavyâkaraṇa*, by Hemacandra, with a Commentary.

The work is interesting, because it is based rather on Çâka-tâyana than on Pânini's grammar. Complete copies are very rare, though the eighth chapter on the Prakrit dialects is met with frequently. With the *Haimavyâkaraṇa* agrees the *Kriyâratna*, a book on conjugation of verbs by Guṇaratnasûri, a Jaina. Besides there are two grammatical works which I was unable to identify during a cursory inspection. I must therefore content myself for the present with stating their titles. They are 1st, *Çabdâsobhâ*, and 2nd, *Ṛijuprajñavyâkaraṇa* (a large fragment of an elementary grammar). Lastly Manuscripts of the *Vaiyâkaraṇabhûshana*, and of the *Vâkyaprakâça* were obtained. The latter treats of syntactical questions.

V. Koshas.

Among the MSS. of Koshas, the following more important ones may be mentioned. The *Amarakosha* with the Commentaries of Râyamukuṭa, Bhânudîkshita, and Liṅgabhaṭṭa, the *Viçvakosha*, the *Dhanamjayakosha*, the *Nânârthamâlâ*, and some smaller glossaries, such as the *Nighaṇṭuçesha* of Hemacandra. The latter work gives the names of trees, bushes, creepers, vegetables, grasses, and species of corn, in six Kâṇḍas and 200 Çlokas.

VI. Dharma.

In this branch three new Smṛitis, attributed respectively to

Kaçyapa, Daksha, and Likhita, came to light. All three treat of the Âcâra only. The first consists of Sûtras, prose mixed with verse, and like the Uçanas and Budha Smritis, it seems to be a fragment of some old Dharmasûtra. For this reason it is of some interest. The Daksha, and Likhita Smritis are both in verse. The former contains eight, the latter six adhyâyas. They distinguish themselves from the tracts usually designated by the names of those Rishis through their greater extent. Possibly they may be fragments of the large old Daksha and Likhita Dharmasûtras. Of a comparatively greater importance is the acquisition of a good old MS. of the entire Vâsishtha Smṛiti, in Sûtras mixed with verse. Most of the MSS. bearing this title contain seven or ten adhyâyas, and are styled Laghu Vâsishtha, the small Vâsishtha. The Calcutta edition of this work has twenty-one adhyâyas, and one MS. in my possession breaks off in the twenty-ninth chapter. The MS. now found has twenty-nine chapters, and the manner of the conclusion which ends with an invocation of Vasishtha, the son of Mitra and Varuṇa, leaves no doubt that it is complete. I am not aware that another complete MS. exists.

Besides these Smritis a copy was procured of the Gautamiyâ Mitâksharâ, the well known commentary of Haradatta on Gautama's Institutes of Law. This MS., which was copied at Belgaum, offers a redaction of the text, which stands between that of a Puṇa MS. in my possession, and that of the MS. belonging to the Asiatic Society of Bengal. Further, I procured copies of the Subodhini by Viçveçvara on the Mitâksharâ, of the Dattakaustubha by Anantadeva, of the Dattârka, of the Smṛitikaumudî, of the Vyavahâroddyota by Dinakara, of the Madanaratnâkara, of the Smṛitiratnâkara, and of the Prayogapârijata. Lastly, I acquired a very old MS. of the Mitâksharâ, copied in the Çaka year 1389 or 1467 A. C., which may prove of great service for the restitution of the text of the famous law book. A superficial comparison of the text of the chapter on Inheritance with the Calcutta edition and Colebrooke's Translation, seems to show that the readings of this MS. agree mostly with those adopted by the oldest commentator, Viçveçvara.

VII. Astronomy.

Only one of the older Siddhântas, the Vṛiddhavâsishtha, was obtained for copying.

VIII. Medicine.

In this branch MSS. were obtained of two ancient works, the Caraka and Âtrei Samhitâs. The former book, composed in Sûtras, is rare, and the latter, I believe, had not been obtained by Europeans hitherto. To these may be added the Dhanvantarini-ghaṇṭu, and the Sârasamuccaya of Kalhana, the son of Bilhana, on horses and diseases of horses.

IX. *Çilpaçastra.*

Four books under this title were obtained from Ashte, viz. the *Pûrtakamalâkara*, work on the consecration of wells, tanks, &c., by *Kamalâkara Bhaṭṭa*. and three treatises of a *Sûtradhâra*, or carpenter, *Çrikshetrâtmajabhṛinmaṇḍana* on the construction of temples and houses, and the manufacture of images of the gods.

X. Printed books, Documents in the Vernacular and English, and Curiosities.

Under this head I have to mention:

1. A printed Commentary on the *Bhâratacampû*, by *Râoji Mahârâj Upâdhyâya* to H. H. the *Râjâ* of Kolhapur, presented by the author.
2. A Commentary on a passage of the *Bhâgavata* by the same, presented by the same.
3. A history of the former state of Nargund, prepared according to oral tradition, and written documents in the hands of a Brahmin at Nargund, by the present *Mâlkarî* (in Marathi), and presented by the same.
4. List of the *Konkaṇasth* Brahman families, according to their *Gotras* (copied from a MS. at Ashte).
5. A list of the *Konkaṇasth* families studying the *Âpastamba-çâkhâ* (copied from a MS. at Ashte).
6. A list of the spiritual heads of the *Mâdhvas* (from the same place).
7. A genealogy of *Çamkarâcârya* (from the same place).
8. A history of the town of *Karhâḍ* (*Kurrâr*), presented by Mr. Arthur, Collector of Sattara.
9. Copies of two Maps of the World according to the Hindu system (from the library of Mr. Dikshit at Sattara).
10. Copies of three Inscriptions from Kolhapur.
11. A set of Sacrificial Implements, used by the *Lingâyats*, from Dharwar.

In concluding this sketch of the results of my tour, I cannot omit to acknowledge my great obligations to the Collectors of Sattara, Belgaum, and Dharwar, to the Political Resident at Kolhapoor, and to the Educational Inspector S.D., who assisted me in various ways with the greatest kindness and readiness. I have also to mention the great assistance which I received from a number of native gentlemen, especially from Mr. Gopâl Nene, Head Master of the Anglo-Vernacular School, Sattara, Mr. Nârayan Baput, Deputy Educational Inspector, Sattara, and Mr. Vâman Agarkar, Assistant Deputy Educational Inspector, Sattara, Mr. Hari K. Sohoni, Moon-siff at Ashte, Mr. Khrishṇarâo Bhikaji, Head Master English School, Kolhapur, Mr. Cambasappa Basvanappa, Deputy Educational Inspector Belgaum, Mr. Venkaṭaraṅga, Principal Belgaum Training School, Mr. Bhujâṅgrâo Hulgoleskar, Assistant in the same School,

Mr. Nâgeshrâo, Deputy Educational Inspector, Dharwar, and the Mâlkarî of Nargund.

Amongst these Mr. Nene, Mr. H. K. Sohoni, Mr. Bh. Halgal-
kar, Mr. Kriṣṇnarâo Bhikaji, and the Malkari at Nargund have
kindly undertaken the task of supervising the copying of the MSS.
selected by me.

8. Finally I beg to state, that the funds placed by Govern-
ment in my hands will not be exhausted, even when all the MSS.
ordered at present have been paid for, and that with a further
grant it would be possible, at least to double the extent of the
collection. Should I, therefore, be permitted to continue my labours
of collecting, and should the Government see fit to unite with the
newly acquired MSS. the older already existing collections, it would
be possible to form a Sanskrit library, which might go far towards
satisfying the wants of our Sanskrit students, and encourage them
to make independent researches.

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Bombay, 12th February 1867.